

TORSION OF RODS

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A solid circular steel shaft, rigidly fixed at one end and consisting of two segments, is subjected to the torsional loads shown in Fig.1.

Fig.1. Problem diagram

It is required to construct the torque diagram and calculate the values of the maximum shear stresses in each section of the shaft, as well as the angles of twist at the characteristic cross-sections. In the calculations, use the shear modulus. $G = 0,8 \cdot 10^5 \text{ MPa} \approx 0,8 \cdot 10^6 \text{ kg/sm}^2$.

We calculate the values of the torques at the characteristic cross-sections of the shaft, starting from the free end.

1. Section plane:

$$x = 2 \text{ m,}$$

$$M_t = 0$$

2. Section plane:

$$x = 1 + 0$$

$$M_t = -100 \cdot 1 = -100 \text{ N} \cdot \text{m}$$

3. Section plane:

$$x = 1 - 0$$

$$M_t = -100 + 400 = 300 \text{ N} \cdot \text{m}$$

4. Section plane:

$$x = 0$$

$$M_t = 300 \text{ N} \cdot \text{m}$$

The torque diagram is shown in Fig.2. In the first section, the torque has a constant value, while in the second section, it varies linearly. At the cross-section corresponding to the boundary between the sections, the torque experiences a sudden change due to a concentrated moment of 400 N·m.

The maximum shear stresses in each section of the shaft and the angles of twist are calculated.

Section one ($D_1 = 4 \text{ sm}$)

$$J_p = \frac{\pi \cdot (D_1)^4}{32} = \frac{\pi(4)^4}{32} = 25,13 \text{ sm}^4,$$

$$W_p = \frac{J_p}{R_1} = \frac{25,13}{2} = 12,57 \text{ sm}^3,$$

$$\tau_{\max} = \frac{M_t^{\max}}{W_p} = \frac{300 \cdot 10}{12,57} = 239 \frac{\text{kg}}{\text{sm}^2} = 23,9 \text{ MPa.}$$

$$\varphi_1 = \frac{M_t \cdot l}{G \cdot J_p} = \frac{300 \cdot 10 \cdot 100}{0,8 \cdot 10^6 \cdot 25,13} = 0,0149 \text{ rad} = 0^\circ 51'$$

Section two ($D_2 = 3 \text{ sm}$)

$$J_p = \frac{\pi(D_2)^4}{32} = \frac{\pi(3)^4}{32} = 7,95 \text{ sm}^4,$$

$$W_p = \frac{J_p}{R_2} = \frac{25,17,95}{1,5} = 5,3 \text{ sm}^3,$$

$$\tau_{\max} = \frac{M_t^{\max}}{W_p} = \frac{100 \cdot 10}{5,3} = 189 \frac{\text{kg}}{\text{sm}^2} = 18,9 \text{ MPa.}$$

$$\varphi_2 = \frac{1}{G \cdot J_p} \cdot \Omega_{M_t} = -\frac{\frac{1}{2} \cdot 100 \cdot 10 \cdot 100}{0,8 \cdot 10^6 \cdot 7,95} = -7,86 \cdot 10^3 \text{ rad} = -0^\circ 27'$$

Fig.2. Shear and bending moment diagrams M_t and φ

The angle of twist of the second section of the shaft was calculated using the area under the torque diagram.

The angle of rotation of the shaft's end section is determined.

$$\varphi = \varphi_1 + \varphi_2 = 0^\circ 51' - 0^\circ 27' = 0^\circ 24'.$$

The end section rotates clockwise. The angle of twist diagram of the shaft is shown in Figure 2. In the first section, the angles of twist vary linearly, whereas in the second section they vary according to a quadratic parabolic law

References:

1. Э.Ф. Винокуров. А.Г. Петрович. Л.И. Шевчук. Сопротивлению материалов расчетно-проектировочные работы. Минск “Вышэйшая школа”. 1987. -227стр.
2. Н.М. Атаров, Ю.Д. Насонкин “Примеры решения задач по сопротивлению материалов”. Учебное пособие. Москва 1990. -136 стр.
3. Khasanov B. B. “Determination of the Angular Velocity of the Driving Link at the Moment of Driving Forces”. Spanish Journal of Innovation and Integrity. ISSN: 2792-8268 Volume: 33, Aug-2024. <http://sjii.indexedresearch.org>
4. Хасанов Б.Б. “РАСЧЕТ СТАТИЧЕСКИ ОПРЕДЕЛИМОЙ СТЕРЖНЕВОЙ СИСТЕМЫ”. ISSN: 2582-4686 SJIF 2021-3.261, SJIF 2022-2.889, 2023-5.384 ResearchBib IF: 8.848 / 2024. Multidisciplinary journal of science and technology, VOLUME-4, ISSUE-12. 4(12), 292–295. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14501838>
5. Erkin Nematov, Mukhiddin Khudjaev, Botir Khasanov. “Development of a mathematical model of dynamic characteristics of a drive with a planetary mechanism”. E3S Web of Conferences 258, 08022 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1051/e3sconf/202125808022>
6. Mukhiddin Khudjaev, Erkin Nematov, Doston Khurramov, Botir Khasanov. “Modeling the process of force load generation at the initial periodic change in pressure (a plane problem)”. E3S Web of Conferences 258, 08020 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1051/e3sconf/202125808020>.
7. B.B. Xasanov., “BURALISH DEFORMATSIYASI”. TECHNICAL SCIENCE RESEARCH IN UZBEKISTAN, 1(5), 547–551. Retrieved from. ISSN (E): 2992-9148 ResearchBib Impact Factor: 9.576 / 2023. VOLUME-1, ISSUE-5 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10448458>
8. Khudjaev M. Shakov V. Khasanov B. “Modeling fluid outflow from a channel consisting of a cylindrical section of a constant radius, and an expanding outlet section”. WEB OF SCIENTIST: INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH JOURNAL ISSN: 2776-0979, Volume 3, Issue 4, April., 2022. <https://wos.academiascience.org>

